

GEO MORPHOMETRY 2021 PERUGIA, ITALY

SEPT
13 - 17
2021

Geomorphometry 2020/2021 – Scientific program

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Topics of the conference

- Use of Digital Elevation, Terrain and Surface Models
- High resolution data collected with LiDAR, photogrammetry and satellite imagery
- Automated surface analysis with machine learning and new algorithms
- Measurements and simulations Earth surface changes
- 3D and 4D dynamics of Earth surface
- Morphometric techniques for climate change studies
- Modeling extreme processes and natural hazards on the Earth surface
- Marine Geomorphometry and bathymetry data
- Geomorphometry for urban areas and cultural heritage
- Planetary morphometry
- Professional and industrial applications of Geomorphometry

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SEPTEMBER 13

USE OF DIGITAL ELEVATION, TERRAIN AND SURFACE MODELS (I)

Morning session

Jozef Minár , Marián Jenčo and Ian S. Evans	Short	PDF VID
<i>What does land surface curvature really mean?</i>	Paper	
Cheng-Zhi Qin , Peng Liang and A-Xing Zhu	Short	PDF VID
<i>Two case-based classification strategies of automatically selecting terrain covariates for building geographic variable-environment relationship</i>	Paper	
(published as full paper in Transactions in GIS)		
Fran Domazetović , Ante Šiljeg and Ivan Marić	Short	PDF VID
<i>Guidelines for optimization of terrestrial laser scanning surveys over gully erosion affected areas</i>	Paper	
Alexey Victorov, Olga Trapeznikova and Timofey Orlov	Short	PDF VID
<i>Probabilistic behavior modeling of morphometric parameters for thermokarst plains with fluvial erosion in Cryolithozone</i>	Paper	
Keynote talk: Marco Cavalli , Stefano Crema and Lorenzo Marchi	Short	PDF VID
Sediment connectivity assessment through a geomorphometric approach: review of recent applications	Paper	
John Gallant	Short	PDF VID
<i>The surface stream function: representing flow topology with numbers</i>	Paper	
John Gallant	Short	PDF VID
<i>The D8 implementation of the surface stream function</i>	Paper	

SEPTEMBER 13

USE OF DIGITAL ELEVATION, TERRAIN AND SURFACE MODELS (II)

Afternoon session

Marina Metes , Kristina Hopkins, Labeeb Ahmed, Sam Lamont, Peter Claggett and Greg Noe	Short PDF VID
<i>Mapping stream and floodplain geomorphic characteristics with the Floodplain and Channel Evaluation Tool (FACET) in the Mid-Atlantic Region, United States</i>	Paper
Adeyemi Olusola	Short PDF VID
<i>Lithology and channel network initiation and orientation: a case study of upper Ogun River Basin, Southwestern Nigeria</i>	Paper
Priyank Patel , Sayoni Mondal and Rajarshi Dasgupta	Short PDF VID
<i>Morphometric and channel erosivity analysis of lateritic gully catchments using high resolution DTM and repeat survey Structure-from-Motion datasets</i>	Paper
(published as full paper in Transactions in GIS)	
Francesco Bucci , Michele Santangelo, Francesco Mirabella, Andrea Mazzoni and Mauro Cardinali	Short PDF VID
<i>Drainage inversion revealed by geomorphometric analysis of fluvial terraces</i>	Paper
Mihai Nicolita	Short PDF VID
<i>Burial mound detection using geomorphometry and statistical methods: pixels versus objects</i>	Paper
Richard Feciskanin and Jozef Minár	Short PDF VID
<i>An optimization of triangular network and its use in DEM generalization for the land surface segmentation</i>	Paper
(published as full paper in Transactions in GIS)	
Vincent Lecours and Michael Espriella	Short PDF VID
<i>Can multiscale roughness help computer-assisted identification of coastal habitats in Florida?</i>	Paper
Charles Holderman, Steve Kopp and Nawajish Noman	Short PDF VID
<i>A New Analytic Framework and Notebook for Terrain Analysis</i>	Paper

SEPTEMBER 14

DYNAMICS OF EARTH SURFACE: AUTOMATED SURFACE ANALYSIS AND MODELIZATION (I)

Morning session

<p>Peter Guth</p> <p><i>Using high-resolution lidar point clouds to evaluate 1-3 arc second global digital elevation models</i></p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Tera Geoffroy and Peter Guth</p> <p><i>Using high-resolution ICESat-2 point clouds to evaluate 1-3 arc second global digital elevation models</i></p> <p>(published as full paper in Transactions in GIS)</p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Daniele Pinton, Alberto Canestrelli, Christine Angelini, Benjamin Wilkinson, Peter Ifju and Andrew Ortega</p> <p><i>Estimating the spatial distribution of vegetation height and ground level elevation in a mesotidal salt marsh from UAV LiDAR derived point cloud</i></p> <p>(published as full paper in Earth Surface Processes and Landforms)</p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Guanghai Hu, Liyang Xiong and Guoan Tang</p> <p><i>Mathematical vector framework for land surface curvature calculation from triangulated irregular network</i></p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Announcement of Lifetime Achievement Award: Michael Hutchinson</p>	<p>PDF VID</p>
<p>Keynote talk: Michael Hutchinson - Reflections on adding the Z dimension to earth system analysis</p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Sebastiano Trevisani</p> <p><i>Geomorphometric features selection based on intrinsic dimension estimation</i></p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>
<p>Kacper Jancewicz, Piotr Migoń, Wioleta Porębną and Milena Różycka</p> <p><i>High-resolution geomorphometry – a tool for better understanding the genesis and contemporary processes in erosional sandstone landscapes</i></p>	<p>Short PDF VID Paper</p>

SEPTEMBER 14

DYNAMICS OF EARTH SURFACE: AUTOMATED SURFACE ANALYSIS AND MODELIZATION (II)

Afternoon session

Tomislav Hengl and Leandro Parente	Short PDF VID
<i>Continental-scale Digital Terrain Model for EU based on Ensemble Machine Learning</i>	Paper
Gaurav Sinha and Samantha Arundel	Short PDF VID
<i>Automated Extraction of Areal Extents For GNIS Summit Features Using the Eminence-Core Method</i>	Paper
Olga Ishalina , Dmitrii Bliakharskii and Igor Florinsky	Short PDF VID
<i>Detection of crevasses using high-resolution digital elevation models: Comparison of geomorphometric modeling and texture analysis</i>	Paper
(published as full paper in Transactions in GIS)	
Carlos Grohmann , Guilherme Garcia, Alynne Affonso and Rafael Albuquerque	Short PDF VID
<i>Coastal dune modelling from airborne LiDAR, terrestrial LiDAR and Structure from Motion–Multi View Stereo</i>	Paper
(published as full paper in Computers & Geosciences)	
Bartłomiej Szypuła	Short PDF VID
<i>DEM from topographic maps - as good as DEM from LiDAR?</i>	Paper
Anna Dedkova , Igor Florinsky and Nikolay Djuzhev	Short PDF VID
<i>Analysis of topography of silicon wafers and wafer-based structures by geomorphometric modeling</i>	Paper
Peter L. Guth and Morgan E. Kane	Short PDF VID
<i>Evaluation of slopes calculated from TanDEM-X digital elevation models at 3 spatial resolutions</i>	Paper
Ivan Marić , Ante Šiljeg, Fran Domazetović and Neven Cukrov	Short PDF VID
<i>A framework for using handheld 3D surface scanners in quantifying the volumetric tufa growth</i>	Paper
Ante Šiljeg , Vlatko Roland, Lovre Panda, Ivan Marić, Fran Domazetović, Silvija Šiljeg and Rina Milošević	Short PDF VID
<i>Development of the new methodological framework for multiscale modeling of urban pluvial flooding</i>	Paper

SEPTEMBER 15

MODELING GEOMORPHOLOGICAL PROCESSES (I)

Morning session

Andrei Dornik , Lucian Drăguț, Marinela Adriana Chețan, Takashi Oguchi, Yuichi Hayakawa and Mihai Micu	Short PDF VID
<i>Towards a consistent set of land-surface variables for landslide modelling</i>	Paper
Mihai Niculita	Short PDF VID
<i>Landslide topographic signature prediction using segmentation of roughness and Random Forest</i>	Paper
Stefan Steger	Short PDF VID
<i>The role of pre-landslide morphology in statistical modelling of landslide-prone areas</i> (published as full paper in Geomorphology)	Paper
Shui Yamaguchi and Mio Kasai	Short PDF VID
<i>Incorporating ground cracks in the estimation of post-seismic landslide susceptibility</i>	Paper
Keynote talk: Igor Florinsky, Sergey Filippov and Alexander Govorov	Short PDF VID
3D marine geomorphometry for the Arctic Ocean	Paper
Margaret Dolan , Lilja Bjarnadóttir, Terje Thorsnes, Markus Diesing and Shyam Chand	Short PDF VID
<i>Geomorphometry in the deep Norwegian Sea</i>	Paper
Queralt Guerrero , Ariadna Salabarnada, Amadeu Deu and Marcelo Devincenzi	Short PDF VID
<i>Marine geophysical investigations for offshore wind farms and submarine interconnection cables</i>	Paper
Meeting of the International Society for Geomorphometry	

SEPTEMBER 15

MODELING GEOMORPHOLOGICAL PROCESSES (II) - Afternoon session

Ivica Milevski , Marjan Temovski, Balazs Madarasz, Zoltan Kern and Zsofia Ruszkiczay-Rudiger	Short PDF VID
<i>Geomorphometry of the cirques of Shar Mountain</i>	Paper
Ivica Milevski , Bojana Aleksova and Sonja Lepitkova	Short PDF VID
<i>Geomorphometric characteristics of the high mountains in North Macedonia</i>	Paper
Ian Sylvester Evans , Nicholas J. Cox, Mihai Niculita and David Milledge	Short PDF VID
<i>Hypsoclinometric evidence of the degree of modification of mountains by glacial erosion</i>	Paper
Simone Tarquini , Massimiliano Favalli, Melissa Pfeffer, Mattia De' Michieli Vitturi, Sara Barsotti and Gro Pedersen	Short PDF VID
<i>Assessing the impact of lava flows during the unrest of Svartsengi volcano in the Reykjaness peninsula, Iceland</i>	Paper
Giuseppe Amatulli , Tushar Sethi, Longzhu Shen, JaimeRicardo, Garcia-Márquez, Jens Kiesel and Sami Domisch	Short PDF VID
<i>A new and extendable global watershed and stream network delineation using GRASS-GIS</i>	Paper
Atrayee Biswas , Sunando Bandyopadhyay and Abhijit Chakraborty	Short PDF VID
<i>Characterizing Gully Morphology using Structure-from-Motion (SfM) in Garhbeta Badlands, West Bengal, India</i>	Paper
Badal Pokharel , Massimiliano Alvioli and Samsung Lim	Short PDF VID
<i>Relevance of morphometric parameters and completeness of inventories in susceptibility modelling of earthquake-induced landslides</i>	Paper
Massimiliano Alvioli, Michele Santangelo, Federica Fiorucci , Mauro Cardinali, Ivan Marchesini, Paola Reichenbach and Mauro Rossi	Short PDF VID
<i>A data-driven method for assessing the probability for terrain grid cells of initiating rockfalls on a large area</i>	Paper
(published as full paper in Engineering Geology)	
Nada Ait Ayad , Adnane Habib, Khalid Elkhalidi, Abdeloihab Choukri and Abdelmounim Charif	Short PDF VID
<i>Geomorphometric Analysis for Mapping Platforms of the Mazagan Corridor, Morocco</i>	Paper

Best student paper award & best paper award

<p>Best student paper award</p> <p>Daniele Pinton</p>	<p>Daniele Pinton, Alberto Canestrelli, Christine Angelini, Benjamin Wilkinson, Peter Ifju and Andrew Ortega</p> <p><i>Estimating the spatial distribution of vegetation height and ground level elevation in a mesotidal salt marsh from UAV LiDAR derived point cloud</i></p> <p>(published as full paper in Earth Surface Processes and Landforms)</p>	<p>Short Paper PDF VID</p>
<p>Best paper award #1</p> <p>Michael Hutchinson</p>	<p>Michael Hutchinson - <i>Reflections on adding the Z dimension to earth system analysis</i></p>	<p>Short Paper PDF VID</p>
<p>Best paper award #2</p> <p>Federica Fiorucci</p>	<p>Massimiliano Alvioli, Michele Santangelo, Federica Fiorucci, Mauro Cardinali, Ivan Marchesini, Paola Reichenbach and Mauro Rossi</p> <p><i>A data-driven method for assessing the probability for terrain grid cells of initiating rockfalls on a large area</i></p> <p>(published as full paper in Engineering Geology)</p>	<p>Short Paper PDF VID</p>

Summary of Geomorphometry 2021

The sixth Geomorphometry conference, organized in Perugia, Italy by the Research Institute for Geo-Hydrological Protection ([CNR IRPI](#), Perugia) and the Department of Physics and Geology of the University of Perugia ([UniPG](#)), is now over. The organizing committee - Massimiliano Alvioli and Ivan Marchesini (CNR IRPI), Laura Melelli (UniPG) and Peter Guth (US Naval Academy) provided local support also on behalf of the [International Society for Geomorphometry](#).

About 50 researchers from around the world attended the event, mostly by remote connection. The conference only featured oral sessions, with 44 contributions. Three invited keynote talks, by Michael Hutchinson (Australian National University College of Science), Igor Florinsky (Russian Academy of Sciences) and Marco Cavalli (CNR IRPI, Padua) enriched the content of the conference. [Contributions](#) were spread over three days, grouped by topic: “use of digital elevation, terrain and surface models” on day 1, “dynamics of earth surface: automated surface analysis and modelization” on day 2, and “modeling geomorphological processes” on day 3.

All of the sessions demonstrated that quantitative analysis of the Earth's surface is closely related to the scale at which the surface itself is described/represented. Research on a global scale (e.g. aimed at the definition of accurate hydrographic networks) was counterbalanced by studies that focused on centimetric portions of Earth's surface (e.g. small plates where accretion of tufa/travertine is studied). A related relevant topic was the comparison of lidar data with global (or quasi-global) DEMs and among different global DEMs, using different methods in many

study areas. Explicit comparisons highlighted that, in selected areas representative of most existing settings, Copernicus DEM is the best performing; other comparisons in different areas and methods favored MERIT DEM. In all cases, lidar data represents the benchmark. Despite that, a discussion highlighted that peculiar applications may not be so sensitive to details represented in elevation data from lidar and/or SfM measurements to justify the much higher cost. There also have been an explicit proposal to merge global and local elevation data, already existing and available online for Europe.

This also led to a discussion about the characteristic scale of terrain analysis, and a few presentations described multi-scale approaches as mature tools for a variety of application. Mainly, they described multi-scale methods for estimation of terrain roughness, curvatures, and landform mapping. The relationship between multi-scale approaches and characteristic scale may lead to need of optimization of numerical parameters for terrain analysis and classification. A few presentations focused on the geomorphological and physical meaning of maps derived from digital terrain models (such as curvatures) or on the definition of new functions aimed at representing the topology of surface water flow directions or the selection of features (derived from DEM) which are relevant in supervised classification applications.

Applications of geomorphometry concepts and algorithms to other disciplines/topics have been numerous and included tectonics, soil erosion, landslide susceptibility, thermokarst phenomena, river forms, coastal habitat and coastal dunes, crevasses in polar ice, inundated areas, glacial cirques and volcanic eruptions.

One addition to the topics of this year's edition of the conference was specifically commercial and industrial application. The scientific program actually included a few contributions explicitly reporting about industrial processes (microscopic analysis of silicon wafer "topography") and commercial applications (deposition and analysis of submarine cables, rockfall susceptibility along the Italian national railway). Other contributions, even if not specifically commercial, highlighted the use of algorithms borrowed from computer graphics for terrain segmentation, and adaptation of general-purpose software for marine geomorphometry. Moreover, commercial and industrial applications were one of the key topics – along with the role of local/global elevation data – for a proposed session at the upcoming European Geoscience Union General Assembly, prepared by a few of the participants of Geomorphometry 2021.

Contributions presented at the conference are available as peer-reviewed short papers from the [book of Proceedings](#) of the 2020 submissions (CNR Edizioni, Rome), or on [Zenodo](#), for new submissions. Most of the presentations are also available as PDF and/or video recording at the [conference website](#); a few of the contributions also have a link to published papers, either on the special issue "Advances in geomorphometry" in the journal [Transactions in GIS](#).